

Mercaptoquinazoline Dyes. Synthesis of 2-Mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichloro-4-stilbenyl)-6-aryldiazo-4-oxoquinazoline Dyes and their Application

N. M. NAIK and K. R. DESAI*

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

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The azo dyes of the type 2-mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichloro-4-stilbenyl)-6-aryldiazo-4-oxoquinazoline have been synthesised by reaction of 5-nitro-*N*-acetylanthranilic acid with *p*-tolylthiourea, condensation of the product with 2,4-dichlorobenzaldehyde, reduction with sodium sulphide to the amine, diazotisation and finally coupling with various components. Dyeing properties of these dyes on silk, wool and viscose rayon were assessed. The percentage exhaustion of dye-bath on silk and wool was good to excellent and on viscose rayon it was poor to moderate. A study of the fastness of dyed patterns showed that the dyes were good to very good on silk and wool, and fair to good for viscose rayon.

THE utility of quinazoline derivatives for the production of some commercial dyes and pigments useful both to natural and man made fibers has been known^{1,2}. 4-Oxoquinazoline based azo dyes in which a suitably substituted 4-oxoquinazoline functions as an azo component or as component of reactive dyes have been reported³. A number of yellow, orange and red azo dyes⁴ from 2-(*m*- or *p*-aminophenyl)-4-oxoquinazoline-5-carboxylic acid and azo disperse dyes⁵ from 3-(*p*- or *m*-aminophenyl)-2-methyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolinone have been reported. Several 2-alkylmercapto-3-phenyl-4-oxoquinazolines⁶ and 3-substituted-2-mercapto-4-oxoquinazolines⁷ have been synthesised. Hence, it was thought interesting to undertake synthesis and study of the dyeing properties of the azo dyes based on 2-mercapto-4-oxoquinazoline system. The azo dyes of the following structure were prepared.

where, R = coupling component.

Experimental

2-Mercapto-3-(*p*-tolyl)-6-nitro-4-oxoquinazoline : A mixture of 5-nitro-*N*-acetylanthranilic acid (2.24 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-tolylthiourea (1.66 g, 0.01 mol) was heated in an oil-bath at 150–60° for 2 h, then cooled, extracted twice with hot 5% NaOH (2 × 50 ml) and filtered. The filtrate was cooled and acidified with HCl (1 : 1) and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from absolute ethanol, (60%), m.p. 254°.

2-Mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichlorostilbenyl)-6-nitro-4-oxoquinazoline : A solution of 2-mercapto-3-(*p*-tolyl)-6-nitro-4-oxoquinazoline (3.14 g, 0.01 mol) and 2,4-dichlorobenzaldehyde (1.75 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (80 ml) and 10% NaOH (2 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solvent was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was recrystallised from absolute ethanol, (52%), m.p. 273°.

2-Mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichlorostilbenyl)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline : A suspension of 2-mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichlorostilbenyl)-6-nitro-4-oxoquinazoline (4.71 g, 0.01 mol) in a solution of sodium sulphide (7.2 g, 0.03 mol) in water (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. After cooling the mixture was made acidic with HCl, boiled for 20 min and filtered. Addition of Na₂CO₃ precipitated the free amine, which was recrystallised from absolute ethanol, (74%), m.p. 260°.

Diazotisation of 2-mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichlorostilbenyl)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline : 2-Mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichlorostilbenyl)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline (3.53 g, 0.01 mol) was diazotised in the usual manner. The resulting diazo solution was used for subsequent coupling reaction.

Coupling of diazo solution with various coupling components : The coupling component (0.008 mol) was suspended in water (20 ml). The solution was cooled (5°) and the diazo solution was added to it dropwise with stirring maintaining pH neutral by addition of Na₂CO₃ solution. The stirring was continued for 3 h at 0–5°. The reaction mixture was then heated to 60° and NaCl was added until the colouring material was precipitated. The mixture was stirred for 1 h and the resulting solid was dried and purified from DMF–chloroform.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA

Dye no.	Coupling component (R)	Yield %	M.p.* °C	Nitrogen % :	
				Found	Required
D-1	H-acid	89	308	8.48	8.59
D-2	J-acid	79	378	9.71	9.88
D-3	R-acid	81	268	9.74	9.88
D-4	G-salt	78	300	6.89	7.00
D-5	R-salt	82	320	6.92	7.00
D-6	Chicago acid	75	310	8.50	8.59
D-7	N-Methyl-J-acid	80	317	9.60	9.69
D-8	N-Phenyl-J-acid	84	>320	8.70	8.92
D-9	Schaffer's acid	81	298	7.96	8.04
D-10	2-Naphthylamine-3,6,8-trisulphonic acid	77	252	7.70	7.78
D-11	1-(4'-Sulphophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone	76	295	11.46	11.55
D-12	1-(1'-Sulphophenyl)-3-carboxy-5-pyrazolone	79	312	11.00	11.09
D-13	1-(2',5'-Dichloro-4'-sulphophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone	78	305	10.43	10.55

*All decomposed except no. D-8.

Application :

2% Shade on viscose rayon as direct dyes and on silk and wool as acid dyes : Material and condition of the experiment are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl. no.	Material/Condition	For direct dye	For acid dye
1.	Fabric (g)	2.0	2.0
2.	Dye solution under study (ml ; 1% w/v)	40	40
3.	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (5%, ml)	5	—
4.	NaCl (g)	0.5	—
5.	pH	7.5-8.0	3
6.	MLR	1 : 40	1 : 30
7.	Dyeing time (min)	90	60
8.	Dyeing temp. (°C)	100	100
9.	Total volume of dye-bath (ml)	80	60

The pH for the direct dye was adjusted with (NH₄)₂SO₄ solution. After completion of dyeing the dye-bath was cooled, the fabric was removed and stirred into water (25 ml). The fabric was then squeezed and rinsed with water and resqueezed.

For acid dye, dye-bath (40 ml, 0.1% w/v) with MLR 1 : 30 was adjusted to pH 3 by dilute acetic acid. The sample of fabric was introduced in the dye-bath at room temperature and the temperature was slowly raised to 100° in 15 min. The fabric was worked up in dye-bath for 1 h. The dyeing was terminated by removing the fabric from dye-bath and stirring it into water (40 ml). The fabric was then removed, squeezed and rinsed with water (50 ml) and resqueezed.

Determination of R_f values : 2-Mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichlorostilbenyl)-6-arylozo-4-oxoquinazoline dyes were separated on tlc using benzyl alcohol -

DMF-water (3 : 2 : 2) solvent system. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Dye no.	Colour	λ _{max}	R _f	% Exhaustion		
				Direct dyes		
				Viscose	Silk	Wool
D-1	Violet	535	0.83	42	70	66
D-2	Brown	495	0.81	45	68	62
D-3	Violet	545	0.84	56	75	70
D-4	Violet	510	0.85	54	80	74
D-5	Brown	490	0.80	52	78	72
D-6	Reddish brown	498	0.79	44	82	76
D-7	Maroon	505	0.81	47	68	60
D-8	Red	485	0.83	50	71	69
D-9	Yellow	410	0.68	49	76	71
D-10	Yellow	410	0.79	58	73	65
D-11	Orange	415	0.80	53	70	63
D-12	Orange	415	0.77	46	74	68
D-13	Red	485	0.74	52	78	73

Determination of λ_{max} : Absorption maxima of 2-mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichlorostilbenyl)-6-arylozo-4-oxoquinazoline dyes were determined in water at 28° using a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. The results are given in Table 3.

Exhaustion study of dyes : The percentage exhaustion study of the dyes was performed using the standard procedure. The results are given in Table 3.

Infrared spectra : The ir spectra (KBr) of 2-mercapto-3-(2',4'-dichlorostilbenyl)-6-arylozo-4-oxoquinazoline dyes contained characteristic bands at 3 345-3 475 br (NH and OH), 1 620 (C=O stretch of 4-oxoquinazoline), 1 460-1 480 w (N=N), 1 010-1 040 (C-H out-of-plane deformation of trans-CH=CH) and 1 170-1 185 cm⁻¹ (S=O).

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